

***In Vitro* Studies of Phytochemicals, Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Action of *Terminalia chebula* in the Induction of Apoptosis Against Breast Cancer Cell Lines**

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have long been a vital part of human society for treatment of illness. *Terminalia chebula* Retz. is known as the "King of Medicine" in Tibet due to its unique therapeutic properties and is frequently ranked first among the "Ayurvedic Materia Medica." The whole plant has significant medicinal benefits and has been used to treat a various of human ailments. This study focused on identifying phytochemicals in the methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. Antioxidant activity was assessed using the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay and antibacterial activity was tested using the Mueller-Hinton agar diffusion method. The human breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231 was used to evaluate the anticancer activity. The results revealed the presence of valuable bioactive compounds that contribute to its biochemical activities, including betacyanins, flavonoids, phenolics, terpenoids, glycosides, quinones, steroids, and tannins. The methanolic extract displayed the highest antioxidant activity. Additionally, the extract exhibited antibacterial properties against bacteria such as *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. With an IC₅₀ value of 73.5 µg/ml, the extract showed excellent cytotoxicity in the MDA-MB-231 cell line. Therefore, *Terminalia chebula* Retz. may be a promising candidate for future pharmaceutical applications and medicinal use.

Keywords: *Terminalia chebula*, methanolic extract, Phytochemical analysis, DPPH, MTT assay.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicines are often derived from plants. In modern biomedicine, plants that are rich in natural antioxidants and possess antibacterial properties may serve as future sources of medications [1]. These plants typically contain phenols, flavonoids, and terpenoids, which act as free radical scavengers [2]. Cancer, one of the leading causes of death, is increasingly prevalent worldwide [3]. Many of the chemical compounds that exhibit anticancer properties have been derived from plants *Terminalia chebula* (Family: Combretaceae), commonly known as yellow or chebolic myrobalan in English, Harad in Hindi, and Kadukkai in Tamil, is widely used in many Asian and African countries as a folk remedy. Its seeds have been researched for various therapeutic properties, including homeostatic, antitussive,

laxative, diuretic, and cardiogenic effects [4,5]. Studies have also investigated the effect of methanol extracts from *Terminalia chebula* seeds on the growth of various cancer cell lines [6]. The plant kingdom is a rich source of medicines, with plants being integral to the treatment of a wide range of illnesses and providing a major source of medications worldwide [7]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Terminalia chebula seed was collected from a Ambatur market in Tamil Nadu, India. After thoroughly washing them with purified water, the seeds were dried and ground into a fine powder.

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2.1. PROCEDURE

Twenty-five grams of fine powder of *Terminalia chebula* was placed in the round-bottom flask of the Soxhlet apparatus, and a condenser was connected. Then, 500 mL of methanol was added, and the mixture was heated to initiate the extraction process. Methanol was vaporized and dripped back onto the sample, restarting the cycle each time the solvent level was reached and the flask was refilled. After 120 minutes, a colorless solution was obtained. The solvent extract was then stored and dried for 48 hours to produce the crude extract, which was collected in an Eppendorf tube [8]. This extract was used for phytochemical analysis by using standard procedures [9]

Figure. 1. *Terminalia chebula*

2.2. ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

In a test tube, add 3.7 ml of ethanol, 0.1 ml of extract, and 0.2 ml of DPPH solution. The same amount of ethanol and DPPH were added to the blank. This mixture was incubated at dark room for forty minutes. At 517 nm, these solutions were absorbed for scavenging activity (Table 2) [10].

2.3. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

The bacterial susceptibility to the extract was evaluated using the standardised minimum inhibitory concentration method. There are four different kinds of bacteria: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Salmonella*, and *Escherichia coli*. To make the inoculum, which had antibacterial qualities, the organism's overnight culture was added to the suitable broth. To make the inoculum, the organism's overnight culture was added to the suitable broth. Bacteria were grown at 37°C. Dry filter paper discs (6 mm in diameter) soaked in the sterile *Terminalia*

chebula extract (20 µl) were placed over each inoculate plate. Penicillin and Streptomycin used for the antibiotics. This solution contains 10,000 units/ml of penicillin and 10,000 units/ml of streptomycin. After that, plates were incubated at 37°C for 12 hours. The antibiotics of streptomycin and penicillin were used to prevent bacterial contamination in cell culture. The antibacterial activity was measured by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition.

2.4. ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

The human breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231, which has the passage number 21, was purchased from NCCS. Dulbecco's Minimum Essential Media (DMEM) with low glucose supplemented with 10% FBS, 100 units/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin were used to sustain the cells. The cells were cultivated at 37°C in a humidified environment with 5% CO₂. Following a few passes, cells were seeded for the tests after being cultivated in a 25 cm² culture flask. At 70 to 80% confluence, the trials were conducted. Cells were separated using a 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA solution when they reached confluence [11].

2.5. Cell Proliferation Assay or MTT Assay

The MTT assay was used to evaluate the cytotoxicity of *Terminalia chebula's* methanolic extract [12]. A concentration of 5×10^4 cells/well was maintained for 24 hours after the cells were plated on a 24-well plate. A 100µl medium containing varying concentrations of *Terminalia chebula* methanolic extract (1000–31.2µg/ml) was substituted for the medium after the cells had been incubated for 24 hours. The sample dilution was taken in a 6 eppendorf tube, each of which contained 500µl of DMEM without serum medium. One millilitre of *Terminalia chebula* extract was pipetted out and mixed into the first tube, and then 500µl from the same tube was pipetted out into the second tube. For the remaining tubes, this procedure was repeated, and they were incubated for twenty-four hours.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Phytochemical Analysis

Phytochemical compounds have qualitatively analyzed by different tests. Numerous phytochemicals, like acids, alkaloids, betacyanins, carbohydrates, glycosides, phenols, quinones, flavonoids, terpenoids, and tannins were detected in the methanolic extract. (Table.1)

Table 1. Phytochemical studies of methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula*.

S.No	Phytoconstituents	Inference
1	Acids	Present
2	Alkaloids	Present
3	Anthocyanins & Betacyanins	Absent & Present
4	Carbohydrates	Present
5	Cardiac Glycosides	Absent
6	Coumarins	Absent
7	Flavonoids	Present
8	Glycosides	Present
9	Phenol	Present
10	Protein	Absent
11	Quinones	Present
12	Saponins	Absent
13	Starch	Absent
14	Steroids	Present
15	Tannins	Present
16	Terpenoids	Present

3.2.ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

DPPH radical scavenging properties were assessed at various doses (20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 mg/ml, respectively). When compared to the control ascorbic acid, the *Terminalia chebula* extract showed the highest IC₅₀ values at 75 mg/ml. The current investigation demonstrated that the scavenging activity of methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula*

was close to that of ascorbic acid (Figure.2). According to the results, methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* exhibits a strong DPPH free radical scavenging action. With higher concentrations, the methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* exhibits the highest scavenging action. This might be because *Terminalia chebula*'s extract has the ability to donate some electrons.

Figure 2. Antioxidant Activity of *Terminalia chebula*.

3.3 Antimicrobial activity

The agar diffusion method was used to measure the diameter of the growth of inhibition zones in order to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the *Terminalia chebula* extract at a 20 μ l concentration and against the tested organisms. Gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria were both susceptible to the extract's wide range of antibacterial activity. Four organisms were used to test the methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula*: *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Bacillus cereus*, which are Gram negative bacteria, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, which are Gram positive bacteria. The findings indicate that *Terminalia*

chebula methanolic extract exhibited a zone of inhibition against the pathogens. *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* were all inhibited by a 17 mm-diameter zone of inhibition of *Terminalia chebula*. (Table 2 and Figure 3).

Table 2. Anti-microbial activity of methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* Zone of inhibition mm.

Organisms	Antibiotic 20 μ l	Sample extract 20 μ l
<i>E. coli</i>	14mm	15mm
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	14mm	15mm
<i>Bacilli cereus</i>	16mm	17mm
<i>S. aureus</i>	15mm	17mm

Figure 3. Antimicrobial activity of methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* - zone of inhibition.

3.4 ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

Using an in vitro cytotoxicity assay, the cytotoxic effects of *Terminalia chebula* methanolic extract on human MDA-MB-231 cells (breast cancer cells) were assessed. *Terminalia chebula's* effects on the cell survival of human breast cancer cells, such as MDA-MB-231 cells, were measured at various time intervals with varying concentrations (31.2,62.5,125,250,500,1000 µg/ml). At various concentrations, the cell viability was descent in comparison to the control. The MDA-MB-231 cells, which resemble breast cancer cells, were treated with

Terminalia chebula for 72 hours. Following treatment, the treated cells shrink and lost contact with their adjacent cells (Table 3 and Figure.5).

For the in vitro cytotoxicity test, this study shows that *Terminalia chebula* has good cytotoxicity. The 73% formazan formation was used to calculate *Terminalia chebula's* IC50, which was then compared to the control cells. Following *Terminalia chebula* treatment, the viability of MDA-MB-231 cells was significantly decreased in a dose-dependent manner, with a maximal IC50 value of 73.5 µg/ml (Figure.4).

Table 3. Illustrate cell viability of methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* against MDA-MB-231 cell line.

S.No	Concentration	Optical density	% of Cell Viability
1	1000	27.3	30.2
2	500	39.3	43.5
3	250	40.2	44.5
4	125	40.3	44.6
5	62.5	52.6	58.3
6	31.2	64.5	71.5
7	Control	90.2	

Figure. 4. The cell viability of methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* against MDA-MB-231 cell line. The viability concentration at 50% (IC50) is 73.5 µg/ml

Figure. 5. Anti cancer effect in methanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* on MDA-MB-231 cell lines.

4.DISCUSSION

Plant extract contains various phytochemicals, which are nonnutrient compounds with biological activity that may have useful medicinal applications. Numerous phytochemicals have been shown to have a wide spectrum of properties that could aid in preventing chronic illnesses [13].

Terminalia bellerica fruit extract contains, flavonoids, phenol, tannins, and alkaloids. The phytochemicals alkaloid in the fruit extract might have prevented the microorganism by damaging the energy-producing enzymes, damage the cell membranes, and block the production of structural elements. Phenol may have prevented the fungus multiplication. Tannins in *Terminalia bellerica* fruit extract may have

inhibited the growth of microorganisms [14]. High concentration of proline to inhibit the protein production [15].

It is commonly recognized that polyphenols have antioxidant properties and can help chemotherapy to avoid several types of cancer. It does this by basically interfering with every part of the cell's mechanism, such as blocking the production of new DNA, producing ROS, changing cell survival pathways, halting the cell cycle, disrupting membrane receptors, interacting with enzymes that support the growth and metastasis of cancer, etc [16]. Numerous pathophysiological conditions, including diabetes, cancer, and cardiovascular disease, are significantly influenced by the overproduction of ROS, or oxidative stress [17-19]. Mutations, protein and

nucleic acid damage, abnormal gene expression, and defective DNA linking can all result from an imbalance in reactive oxygen species (ROS) [20-22].

Antioxidants maintain redox equilibrium by acting as scavengers of free radicals and ROS [23]. The connection between tumour growth and antioxidants [24], with some research indicating that by scavenging the body's dangerous free radicals, antioxidants help prevent cancer [25]. However, some studies have suggested that high antioxidant levels might promote the development of cancer [26-28]. Furthermore, *Terminalia chebula* [29] leaf extracts showed the DPPH scavenging activity when extracted with light petroleum, chloroform, aqueous, and ethanol solvents, respectively, according to Birur Eshwarappa et al. (2015)[29] Their IC₅₀ values were 274 ± 2, 201 ± 3, 143 ± 6, and 96 ± 2 µg/mL.

The aqueous extract of *Terminalia chebula* fruit scavenged radical DPPH with an IC₅₀ of 127.1 ± 1.8 µg /mL, according to [30]Chen *et al.*, (2011). According to Lee *et al.*, (2005)[31], triethylchebulate, an aglycone that was isolated from *Terminalia chebula*, with an IC₅₀ value of 2.4 × 10⁻⁵M [31] and a potent free-radical scavenger action. The *Terminalia chebula* decoction product has been shown to suppress bacterial growth and cancer. It has been demonstrated that the *Terminalia chebula* decoction product inhibits both cancer and bacterial growth [32].

Chemotherapy is one of the primary methods of treating cancer; however, most of the chemicals employed in this treatment are harmful to cells and can have teratogenic, carcinogenic, and genotoxic effects on cells that are not tumours. Consequently, a vital area of Research is the process of finding natural substitutes for medications that are less harmful, more effective, and have fewer side effects. In clinical settings, medicinal plants' active chemicals are employed to halt cancers in their advanced stages. Nowadays, it is believed that these natural substances are very beneficial for the development of anticancer drugs that do not significantly damage host cells.

Natural antioxidants, pigments, sulphur compounds, terpenoids, and polyphenolic compounds found in traditional medicinal plants have been connected to the prevention or treatment of illnesses including

cancer. Therefore, for the treatment of different kinds of cancer, natural products are becoming a significant source of very effective traditional drugs. This plant was chosen for further pharmacological research, which may result in new, naturally produced drugs that are safer and more efficient for the treatment of cancer [33].

One important source was found to be the phytochemicals found in *Terminalia chebula*'s methanolic extract. This investigation revealed that the extract of *Terminalia chebula* possesses both anticancer and antibacterial activity.

5.CONCLUSION

The methanolic extracts of *Terminalia chebula* inhibited the rate of cell proliferation (IC₅₀:73.5µg/ml) and caused cell death in the presence of the pathogenic bacteria (Gram negative bacteria: *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*; Gramme positive bacteria: *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) and reduced the number of cancer cell lines. As a result, future research should focus on using this seed as one of the best medicinal properties for managing cancer cells and pathogenic bacteria in humans.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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